

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: THUCH****FIRST NAME: JAMES****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic Essay writing process (EUCLID 2021, 7-9)
2. Structure for academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 10-11)
3. Plagiarism and its related consequences (EUCLID 2021, 32-35)
4. Main Functions of punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
5. Style guides Documentation (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)

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ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

It is a pleasure to have started my Ph.D. study trip with this initial course of international academic writing. I read through the ACA-40/ACA-401D course pack (Period 1), the study material assigned for this RP one. It is an important reading guide, it introduces new doctoral students like me to the world of academic writing processes, punctuation marks, plagiarism dangers, and the rules of different writing style guides for academic article reports.

The study material (ACA-401/ACA-401coursepack-period 1) is divided into eight main chapters with different sub-headings for better understanding. Not all these chapters are discussed in this report; only the main concepts are identified and given more attention. By the way, it was not easy reading through all the chapters to gain a better understanding of the concepts. But due to my excitement and interest in learning more as a new doctoral student! I could scan and read to understand common academic writing concepts outlined in the guide.

In this course pack, all the chapters are well elaborated, with relevant examples illustrating a practical roadmap for new doctoral students to succeed in this new bumpy road of Ph.D. program study. The assigned video was also supportive in demonstrating how to apply the rules of styles, Turabian styles, and the use of either US or UK English with specific quotation marks. The overall objective of this study material and its related video is to technically support students, especially new doctoral students, to get a better understanding of how to write professional articles, books, conference papers, and other

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academic reports such as empirical theses, and manuscripts in a standard manner (Euclid 2021, 1-72).

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However, due to the conciseness and scope of this assignment (only 3-5 pages report). This response paper discusses only the five main concepts outlined in the sub-heading for a better understanding of this assignment. The selected points for discussion include the academic writing process, article structure, plagiarism dangers, punctuations, and the importance of style guide applications.

2) HE ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING PROCESS

Through reading this fruitful study material about academic article writing processes, it is now clear to me that academic writing is not a once-off activity. But an essential part of a professional development course that every student must go through to be successful in their academic world. On the other hand, this means a student has to, first of all, understand what type of academic writing is at hand to deal with. An idea that gives the student a better understanding of how to plan, define and structure his/her academic essay in an instinctive way of international essay writing style, free of plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 7-8).

Indeed, in reading through the period one study guide, I also understand that academic essay writing is not only an initial course to start with but a mandatory process for the students to understand different types of academic report writing. EUCLID's (2021, 7) guide; for instance, encourages every student to understand that the academic writing roadmap involves an individual writing about a specific topic, question, book, or hypothesis that should follow standard formatting styles and citations of information.

I appreciate that this introductory guide to academic writing procedures is a vital learning guide for me. Indeed, it introduces me to new practical knowledge about the academic essay writing process, which is related to my current study. More notably, the experiences gained about the report writing processes are new skills I am learning for the first time for my betterment in academic writing.

Even though Euclid University initially exposes me to this study, it is an essential course I needed to go through before I embarked on my doctoral thesis venture. This course helps me to know that, as a student, I should always try to identify and define the main topic to read, analyze, and then write an article professionally that conveys a better understanding of the article (EUCLID 2021, 7). Of course, the concrete knowledge gained in this study is not only providing me with the academic foundation to proceed well with the rest of my doctoral study, but it is an experience that makes me more competent in writing my academic essay scripts.

3) STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

In the guide, I also read how to plan and structure the skeleton of professional academic essay writing. The central concept of academic writing, especially in constructing, designing, and writing a response paper, is well understood. What I like about this Euclid study guide is; it is written in a simplified way which helps me to familiarize myself to understand the intended article writing structure. For example, this study guide indicates that an academic article or report must be built and written in four main components: an introduction section, a body message, and a conclusion with required endnote references (EUCLID 2021, 10-11).

According to the ACA-401 guide (2021, 10), an essay introduction which is the initial part of an essay, indicates a sentence statement that introduces the main topic, question, or material being discussed with the intended scope of the report. On the other hand, as explained in the guide, the essay's body should follow the introduction section, structured into specific discussion points to understand an article better. In addition, the guide also reiterated the importance of having a concise conclusion with correct references at the end of the article (EUCLID 2021, 10-11).

Through this reading, I learned about the overall importance of academic essay structure and its importance to my doctoral study. The significance of developing professional writing techniques and skills is relevant to my current study. This critical course will give me more momentum and eagerness to continue learning about academic writing structure and process. However, the kind of knowledge gained here in this section about essay structure tips is relevant and helpful to my doctoral study.

Thanks to Euclid University for introducing this initial module; I would be right to predict that none of us would proceed in writing successful theoretical articles if not taken through this initial academic essay writing structure. And I hope that subsequent courses will also have simplified reading materials for easy understanding and success.

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4) PLAGIARISM

The word plagiarism is defined as the theft or copying of other people's original ideas, information, words, quotes, or books without crediting or acknowledging the source or sources of the information (EUCLID, 2021, 32). However, according to ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (2021) guide, plagiarism is plagiarism; whether it is intentional or unintentional is by all mean unacceptable. As a result, Euclid University reminds students always to try their best to prevent plagiarism by correctly using citations for any information used to enrich academic articles. Besides, the guide also indicates the importance of using in-direct paraphrasing and quoting other scholars' work sources to avert potential penalties for plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34). As defined, potential penalties could involve degrading one's marks to failing grades or even dismissal of students due to plagiarism practices.

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More interestingly, when reading through the guide, I find it more motivating to understand the characteristics of plagiarism and its discredited consequences. This knowledge encourages me to be careful and vigilant in preventing deliberate plagiarism when engaged in any article writing. On the other hand, this carefulness alone will also help to avoid academic dishonesty in my response paper and doctoral thesis reports.

In general, the knowledge and experience revealed in this study material about plagiarism acts; indeed guide me on my way to success in the academic writing process now and even in my subsequent courses. In addition, the technical skills achieved at this stage about how to apply in-text paraphrasing and referencing are, of course, my new skills of knowledge that will empower me to improve my academic article writing.

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5) THE MAIN FUNCTIONS OF PUNCTUATION

The other important concept I also read in this assignment guide was the correct use of punctuation marks. For the clarity of articles, EUCLID's 2021 (16-23) guide encourages suitable usages of particular punctuations such as single or double quotation marks, apostrophes, commas, question marks, colons, and other everyday use punctuations such as bullet points, hyphens, and dashes, especially the n-dash for better structure and formatting of academic writing.

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It can be challenging for non-English students like us to understand and appropriately apply punctuation to understand the articles better. But for my understanding of academic success, I will continue to read and practice to fully understand how to apply punctuation marks for effective academic writing. practically, the skill captured in this section will help me improve the quality of my written articles. As you may be aware, mastering the correct use of punctuation marks would be challenging. However, with more reading processes and practice, we shall be there. Now the experience gained at this level will incrementally improve my academic writing style.

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6) STYLE GUIDES DOCUMENTATION

This sub-section discusses the functionality of style guides that every doctoral student must be familiar with when writing any academic article or thesis (EUCLID 2021, 41). As a matter of rules and regulations, it is a common clue that every school of thought uses specific style guides that dictates how students structure their academic articles.

In fact, before embarking on this initial study, I needed to be made aware of style guides. I am learning this kind of new knowledge for the first time in this particular University course. Nevertheless, it is now clear to me that the backbone of any academic writing is reliant on the best usages of different writing styles.

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As far as this particular course is concerned, it is good to appreciate the way Euclid University orients and introduces new students to this fruitful module of academic writing styles, full of new concepts and skills to learn and adapt for possible success. Otherwise,

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life would be hard for some of us, and not only that, with this course exposure, we would also pass successfully through the academic writing phases. Therefore, through this study guide, I learned a lot about the importance of style guide application, spelling check, paragraph structure, and correct formatting of articles, all for my successful outcome.

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7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, although it was difficult to go over and read every section of the period one study guide, I am confident that enough knowledge and new tips about professional essay writing are well understood. The way this course pack is designed makes it easy to understand the core concepts about the academic writing process, structure, punctuations, plagiarism, and effective writing styles for drafting more convincing and understandable reports to the readers.

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However, To achieve quality doctoral study and success, there is a need for Euclid University to continue providing self-explanatory course guides and instructions, especially for new students to understand and learn more. Of course, having quality reading materials with illustrative concepts (like the ACA-401 guide) will aid active learning and success.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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